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INTERPRETATION OF THE "SUBJECT CONTENT BLOCK" ELEMENTS OF THE TECHNOLOGY SUBJECT CURRICULUM AT THE GENERAL EDUCATION LEVEL BASED ON THE "SYSTEM-STRUCTURE" APPROACH

Ibrahimov F.N.,*Sheki branch of ADPU, doctor of pedagogical sciences,
professor**<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0775-1048>***Ibrahimova S.F.***Sheki branch of ADPU, honored teacher, senior teacher**<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7525628>*

Abstract

In the article, it is emphasized that the curriculum reform is conditioned by the need to ensure the adequacy of the implementation of education to the demands of the 21st century, to train a creative, self-developing personality, and the content of the abilities that must be transformed into the subject of the student who has completed his general education is shown.

The importance of the educator's reference to the "system-structural approach" in the research work both in familiarizing himself with the essence of the educational program and in his practical activities related to its implementation, the relevance of subject-oriented curricula to the content of the scientific field, the attention directed to the mastery of these concepts directly by covering its perfect system of concepts is drawn to the center.

In the article, the "block-scheme" form of the structure of the Technology subject curriculum at the general education level, the general learning results, content lines, learning results on content lines, content standards, integration concepts included in the "Content of the subject" block, generalizations made on the basis of the "system-structure" dialectical approach interpretation is presented.

Keywords. *Educational program; curriculum; subject curriculum; "block-scheme" form; overall learning outcomes; content line; content standards; content elements; educational stages and levels; lines of action; household culture; processing technologies; technical elements; graphic.*

Relevance of the research topic.

Observations show that mistakes are made in the activities of educators in the application of the Technology subject curriculum at the general education level. This has a negative effect on the level of efficiency of the teaching process of Technology. It is undeniable that the level of understanding of any real thing has a determining effect on the results of using it in adequate directions. Based on our scientific observations over the past ten years, we have come to the conclusion that the mistakes manifested in the activities of practical educators in the process of using the Technology subject curriculum are based on a number of reasons, as well as a lack of honest understanding of the essence of the Technology subject curriculum by these subjects. Based on our scientific experience, we believe that "system-structure" approach is the most reliable dialectical method of understanding any existing thing, getting to its essence. The analysis of the materials we have collected gives reason to say that this method has not been used enough in the theoretical and technological directions regarding the discovery of the essence of the Technology subject curriculum and the determination of its application ways. Therefore, we claim that one of the issues that lead to the solution of the problem, which is the basis for the manifestation of the mistake given above, should be formulated as "Interpretation of the elements of the "Content of the Subject" block of the Technology subject curriculum at the general education level based on the "system-structure" approach" and that it should be an actual research topic.

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Interpretation of generalizations formed on the basis of research materials.

It is known that in the 21st century, the main value in the life and development of both society and each of its members is a creative, self-developing personality [14; 16]. Education also cannot exist outside the realities of a changing world. Modern psychology considers the creation of favorable conditions for the discovery and realization of the child's creative abilities as the main goal of education [6; 290-292]. Therefore, since the main value in the modern period is a creative, self-developing personality, the educational process should form creativity and self-development abilities in the child. This, in turn, is based on the following activity, the need to understand and the abilities: 1) logical thinking; 2) critical approach to objects and events of the surrounding world; 3) independent decision-making; 4) change the surroundings at a creative speed; 5) independent acquisition of knowledge; 6) solving practical problems; 7) setting new goals for personality development.

The skills that a student who has completed his general education should acquire - the general learning results are formed as a synthesis and dialectical unification of the results targeted in the teaching process of all subjects taught in general education schools (including the subject of Technology).

It is undeniable that it is of particular importance for the teacher teaching Technology to honestly know the tasks set before the general education (general expected results). However, this is one side of the issue and it is necessary to put the activity related to the educational process into a result-oriented system. Thus, the goal is the system-creating component of the activity. At the same time, it is very important to implement the training process in what content, based on what strategy, based on what evaluation mechanisms, in order to achieve the goal. "The new necessary minimum of education at the levels of general education, knowledge limit, linking the general learning outcomes and skills to be acquired in the subject with the learning outcomes to be achieved at separate levels of general education is considered one of the most important problems of education" [11; 71]. The teacher should be able to find both theoretical and practical answers to all questions related to the learning process. He should know which model he uses in the process of which he is a facilitator and what are the specific features of this model. This model incorporates the superior merits of traditional models (it should not be forgotten that innovation is not a complete denial of the old, such a denial can bring more harm than good) and what success it promises to the real pedagogical process. Based on what we have said, we summarize that the "effective organization of all activities related to the educational process" currently applied in general education schools,

The teacher is one of the subjects of the "enabling function" in the implementation of the educational program. The level of his penetration into the essence of the mentioned program has a conditioning effect on the effectiveness of its activity. Therefore, it is important to refer to the "system-structure" approach both in familiarizing with the essence of the program and in the prac-

tical activities related to its implementation, the analysis of research materials and our work experience brings us to this conclusion.

It should be emphasized here that the essence of the system is determined by its structure and function, that is, by the nature of the relationship between the elements and their behavior, and by the specificity of the relationship between the object and the conditions. Without studying the elements that make up the system and their mutual influence, it is impossible to distinguish the continuous, important and necessary relationships here. Such continuous, important and necessary interaction of elements characterizes the structure of the system. The law of relationships of structural elements acts as an invariant of the system. Without learning and opening the relationship of the elements with the whole formed by them, both the function of the system and the functions of each element with regard to the whole remain in the shadows. The full concept is understood in terms of the system, it is the organization of that system. Each system has its own structure and the function that this structure carries. A system can be viewed as a whole consisting of the unity of its structure and function. Systems differ from each other not only by their structure and functions, but also mainly by the nature of the unity of structure and function, the nature of this unity.

The educational program (curriculum) determines the content of education and the rules of mastering it for different levels of education in accordance with state educational standards [8; 106-107]. The educational program includes the curriculum, curricula for subjects, recommendations on methodical provision, assessment and other relevant educational technologies [7; 173]. Educational curricula are divided into two types according to their nature: functional and personality oriented

Science-oriented curricula are directly oriented to the assimilation of these concepts by covering the field of science and its perfect system of concepts in terms of content. Personality-oriented curricula are distinguished by their direct emphasis on life skills and habits. "Personality-oriented", "pupil-oriented" and "result-oriented" approaches of the curriculum indicate that the student is at the center of the learning process"[13].

Subject curricula (including the Technology subject curriculum): take a balanced and comprehensive approach to learning different skills; enables achievement of content standards using active learning methods; implies constant assessment of students' knowledge and understanding, making corrections during the academic year; ensures the involvement of students in training, preparation and motivation for continuous education; it envisages the use of modern technologies while studying, evaluating students' knowledge, improving their literacy; has adequate training resources and administrative support.[4; 189-190]

The block diagram form of the structure of the subject curriculum (as well as the Technology subject curriculum) can be drawn as follows [9; 38] (see scheme 1)

Scheme 1

Summing up, it can be said that the curriculum of the subject of Technology is a set of documents that reflect all the activities aimed at achieving the general learning results by setting the main goals of the teaching of this subject in secondary schools and are directed to the capabilities and needs of each student. It is intended for teachers, school leaders, textbook authors, parents and the general public. The subject curriculum is the basis of the rules to be prepared in the form of appropriate guidelines for the preparation of textbooks and teaching aids, planning of teaching materials, determination of teaching methods and implementation of teacher training.

In the process of defining content standards, the focus is on the expected balance of the main learning outcomes for the subject (calculation procedural skills, cognitive understanding and problem solving). This curriculum presents key learning outcomes through the interaction of content and action lines to determine what students should "know" and "be able to do".[14]

The document included in the "Introduction" block allows determining the place of the Technology subject among the subjects taught in general education schools, as well as the general definition of the main goals of its teaching.

The teaching of the subject "Technology" in secondary schools creates comprehensive conditions for students to use processing technologies in their independent life, to form their creative abilities, and to continue their education in technical fields. In the training process, students determine the possibilities of technical activity, propose ideas for solving problems, perform simple technological tasks and get the opportunity to evaluate the results. At the same time, the teaching

of this subject lays the foundation for shaping the character of students, their spiritual, intellectual and aesthetic development, and their adaptation to socio-economic conditions by acquiring technological skills appropriate to the era.

In addition, through this subject, students are prepared for productive work in different service areas, their polytechnic worldview is expanded and conscious career choices are ensured.

By studying this subject, students get acquainted with computer equipment and modern technologies in detail, acquire knowledge and skills related to processing technologies in production, and acquire the ability to solve problems.

The purpose of the "Technology" subject is to ensure that students prepare for independent life, mass and promising professions in new socio-economic conditions, acquire general skills and habits, and easily adapt to various conditions based on creative thinking and active activity.

As it is known, "revealing the child's creative possibilities and realizing them, creating favorable conditions for the formation of his personality is one of the main goals of education" [9; 290-292]. There is no doubt that subjects, which are the main enabling components of the implementation of general education, are of high value as an important tool in the formation of the personality of schoolchildren. The "enabling" functions of the subjects are expressed in the "Education Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan" in the following content:

-ensures that students are taught the basics of science, inculcated the necessary knowledge, skills and habits, prepare them for life and work;

-enables physical and intellectual development of students, acquisition of necessary knowledge, formation of civic thinking based on healthy lifestyle and civilized values, inculcation of respect for national and worldly values, determination of rights and responsibilities in front of family, society, state and environment[2; 21-23].

Based on the official state documents, we can say that "... the content of general education subjects aims at the following iyearxic goals by focusing on different levels of education":

- to improve reading, writing and calculation skills in primary education, to form basic knowledge about man, society and nature, elements of logical thinking, aesthetic and artistic taste and other characteristics;

- oral speech and writing culture, communication skills, cognitive activity, the development of logical thinking, the formation of relevant knowledge and ideas about the subjects included in the educational program as well as the development of world civilization, the ability to use modern information and communication tools, events to provide the ability to evaluate and determine their own future directions of action;

-realization of talents and abilities, preparation for independent life and professional choice, formation of an active citizen position, respect for national and universal values, human rights and freedoms and tolerance, free use of modern information and communication technologies and other technical means, acquiring the basics of economic knowledge, communicating in

one or more foreign languages, etc. provide (see [1] for more information).

In the mentioned system of knowledge, skills and habits, what is obtained at different educational levels in the teaching of Technology is included as a component. The relevance of the mentioned components has found its expression in the official document. In accordance with the framework document "Concept of general education in the Republic of Azerbaijan (National Curriculum)", the tasks of the subject "Technology" in secondary schools are defined as follows:

At the primary education level, students are trained in comparison and sorting, primary processing, self-service and cooperative habits, simple design, layout, modeling, design, living nature service skills, measurement, proportion, symmetry and other geometric concepts, the ability to perform simple constructions and creative works. Vaccination is provided.

At the basic education level, by developing the activities intended for the fulfillment of the functional tasks set at the primary education level, improving technological and applied skills, implementing non-simple technological processes, forming creative technical thinking, expanding students' opportunities to use modern information technologies, guiding them to choose a profession, diligence and education in the spirit of creativity is ensured.

The general learning outcomes of the technology subject can be schematically described as follows (scheme 2):

Scheme 2

The content line is the part of the content that is considered necessary to ensure the realization of the general learning outcomes of the subject. Content lines are defined to more clearly describe the content that students will learn and aim to systematize it.

As a result of the study of national and world experience, their comparison and analysis, the below-mentioned content lines of the subject "Technology" have been determined, which serves the purpose of more clearly describing and systematizing the

knowledge and skills that students will acquire: Processing technologies; Technical elements; Household culture; Graphic.

As in all subjects, although the content of the technology subject is enriched from class to class, from simple to complex, from easy to difficult on a concentric basis, the content lines remain unchanged.

It is possible to give a schematic description of the general training results by content lines as follows (Scheme 3.1; 3.2; 3.3; 3.4):

Scheme 3.1

Scheme 3.2

Scheme 3.3

Scheme 3.4

The content lines of the technology subject serve to structure the curriculum and, in this case, conduct reasoning. It should be noted that any concepts or skills included in the content of the subject may not be limited to only one content line. When determining the content lines, it is assumed that each of them will be given equal importance in the teaching of the Technology subject. As the content of the subject varies from grade to grade, the content of each of the lines and their weight in the overall content varies considerably.

A curriculum designed along content lines should cover a wide range of content. Taught in an integrative way, this broad content allows students to understand the interrelationship of various vital knowledge not only within the subject of Technology, but also in other subjects and in real life.

It is emphasized in scientific sources that the content standard is the state requirement set for the level of knowledge and skills of the student [3;468]. The standards for the subject of technology cover the content that is important for all students within the secondary education course, describe the knowledge and skills of students in the subject of technology, determine the issues that every student in the country can and should learn in the field of life sciences, and prepare students for the next level of secondary education.

The new approach to setting the content of the standards envisages that each standard consists of several defined objectives (sub-standards) and is repeated throughout the grades in an appropriately expanding capacity.

The content standards of the technology subject are systematized by classes and represented by the

above four content lines. Each standard goal includes several expected learning outcomes defined according to the primary, secondary education levels. The components of technology teaching and learning are not isolated from each other, but rather they are interconnected and complement each other.

The function of the core standard is to explain the defined learning outcomes in a general way along the content lines. It is related to the functions of sub-standards: it creates a reliable basis for the precise determination of learning objectives; plays an important role in the correct selection of training strategies; ensures integration in training; ensures continuous development of training content; provides summative assessment for classes and subjects.

Implementation of content standards in the subject "Technology" is carried out along the following lines of action: Problem solving; Analysis and reasoning; Non-judgmental; Communication; Presentation.

While action lines are distinct from content lines, they are related to each of them. These lines aim to define and describe ways of acquiring and using content

knowledge, and serve to help students understand the importance of computer science and view it as a set of complex skills.

The student can achieve the content of the subject of Technology through various activities. Different stages of student activity in the process of mastering the content ensure that the acquired knowledge and skills are more solid and long-lasting. Performance standards ensure that students master the content standards for implementing the curriculum. Each performance standard describes what is covered in the grade and what the teacher's role is in achieving the content standard. It should be noted that each performance standard varies across educational levels and grades, with use in all grades. Therefore, it is convenient to adopt these standards in general.

Knowledge and action components of content standards, their classification is as follows (see scheme 3)

Scheme 3

Curriculum theorists have identified verbs that represent all stages of all three taxonomies (cognitive, emotional, psychomotor) considered useful for education to aid standard setters. Verbs are a very important indicator in expressing skills. The verb reflects the stage of taxonomy of the skill. [10; 41]

Taxonomies make learning more consistent and efficient. Taxonomies play a major role in the learning process. They provide the following opportunities: correctly define training goals; correctly define problems and design tasks for students; choose evaluation tools according to the set goals; properly conduct reflection based on learning outcomes; to determine what difficulties students face in learning this or that material.

The formation of knowledge, skills and habits that students can acquire and apply in their daily lives in the educational process requires the teaching of both subjects and the topics they cover in a connected-integrative way. Integration is to form a whole and indivisible image of the world in the thinking of students within

the framework of a certain educational system, to establish structural connections between all content components of training and to systematize them in order to direct them to development and self-development. In modern world experience, they distinguish 3 levels of integration.

Intra-subject integration is the systematization of the facts within the subject, the integration of concepts, knowledge and skills instilled in a certain subject. Integration at such a level can also be considered as the concentration of the given material in separate educational units. This ultimately leads to changing the structure of the subject's content. In this sense, integrated content becomes more innovative, helps students to develop thinking skills with more comprehensive categories. Interdisciplinary integration can be both horizontal and vertical.

Rapid social, cultural and technological changes in the modern world greatly increase the importance of a

global mindset. In this case, in the learning process, students are not passive consumers of the knowledge and skills given in individual subjects, but on the contrary, it leads to being treated as subjects who have a creative attitude towards understanding the world around them. This is possible when the subjects studied at the educational levels and the topics covered by them are taught not separately, but in a connected-integrative way. Interdisciplinary integration is the synthesis of concepts, knowledge, skills and principles covered by two or more disciplines. This integration involves the expression of laws, theories and methods related to one discipline in the study of another discipline. Systematization of the content according to this model not only creates a whole and indivisible image of the world in students' thinking, but also promotes the formation of a new type of knowledge characterized by universal concepts, categories and approaches. Similar and complementary topics of different subjects are planned and taught in such a way that a certain framework is created for them, that is, they are taught simultaneously.

Cross-curricular (trans-subject) is the highest level of integration and includes the synthesis of the main and additional content components covered by the training. That is, with this integration, the content that students learn at school and the content they receive outside of school are synthesized. , it requires both the change of educational paradigms and the idea of forming a new generation in communities.[5; 171]

The teaching of integrative subjects such as life science involves not only intra-subject, interdisciplinary and supra-disciplinary integration, but also the integration of teaching methods and technologies.

Scientific novelty and theoretical significance of the research work.

1) The importance of the application of the "system-structure" approach method, formed as an important branch of the dialectic regarding the discovery of the essence of the technology subject curriculum and the determination of its application methods, has been brought to the attention of researchers; 2) "The solution of one of the cognitive issues that determines the solution to the problem of revealing the essence of the Technology subject curriculum at the general education level and developing its application in the optimal version - the interpretation of the "Technology subject content" block based on the "system-structure" approach" was presented.

Practical significance of the research work. We hope that the solution of one of the important cognitive issues that determine the solution to the problem of revealing the essence of the Technology subject curriculum applied at the general education level and its application in the optimal version - the "interpretation of the "Technology subject content" block" on the basis of the system-structural approach" will be presented in the application of the Technology subject curriculum will have a positive effect on the formation of the environment of elimination of mistakes manifested in the activities of educators.

The result.

1) The level of understanding of any real thing has a determining effect on the results of taking advantage

of it in adequate directions; 2) Mistakes in the activities of educators in the application of the Technology subject curriculum at the general education level have a negative effect on the level of efficiency of the Technology subject teaching process; 3) In the process of using the technology subject curriculum, the basis of the mistakes manifested in the activity of practical educators is based not only on one of the reasons, but also on the lack of honest enough understanding of the essence of the technology subject curriculum by these subjects; 4) "System-structural approach" is the most reliable dialectical method of understanding any existing thing, getting to its essence; 5) The "system-structure" dialectical method of the "system-structure" approach was not used in the theoretical and technological directions regarding the discovery of the essence of the technology subject curriculum and the determination of its application methods; 6) One of the cognitive issues aimed at solving the problem that creates the basis for the manifestations of the error caused by the "gap" regarding the discovery of the essence of the technology subject curriculum and the determination of the ways of its application is "Interpretation of the elements of the "Subject Content" block of the subject curriculum at the general education level based on the "system-structure" approach" and the presented research in this direction benefits the teaching process of our subject.

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TEACHERS' PERCEPTIONS OF FORMING SOCIOCULTURAL COMPETENCE AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN ENGLISH CLASSES

Ilesbekova B.

Kazakh Ablai Khan University of International Relations and World Languages, Almaty, Kazakhstan

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Abstract

This article was written in order to determine the cause of the problem of the formation of a certain competence of students in the English lesson in accordance with the changes made to the education system of Kazakhstan. The question included in the article is aimed at the formation of the current socio-cultural competence of schoolchildren through foreign language lessons. And do all teachers fulfill this requirement, or do they accept sociocultural competence as a necessary and important skill? According to the results of the survey conducted during the writing of the article, it was determined and analyzed how teachers of different levels take responsibility for this competence.

Keywords: *competence, sociocultural competence, formation of sociocultural competence, teachers' perception, English classes*

Introduction

The intense political, social and economic transformations in the society of Kazakhstan under the influence of global development led to radical changes in the education system. The directions in the education system are determined according to the requirements of modern society [1]. In addition, the goals and objectives of education in the education system are constantly updated in the strategic plan of each period. One of them is to educate competent and qualified generation starting from the school walls so that the citizens of the state can become competitive individuals [2].

According to the state program of education and science development of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2020-2025, combining the socio-economic development of the country with science, the main goal is to increase the literacy level of citizens by eliminating regional differences, to learn foreign languages in depth, and to form the competencies inherent in a highly intelligent person [3]. Supplementing the aforementioned legislative program with such directions was directly related to the progress of the modern innovative and integrated borderless society.

The modern education system requires the development of critical thinking ability of a person, the ability to analyze it and express one's point of view in the era of large-scale information flow, as well as to have communication skills. Based on this, a person can overcome any misunderstandings and difficulties through cultural experience in the process of establishing a relationship with a representative of another culture. Cultural awareness and communication skills ensure successful interpersonal dialogue [4]. As a rule, learning and mastering the differences between cultures takes place in foreign language classes. Based on this, it can

be said that sociocultural competence is a component that plays a major role in human development.

That is, the importance of formation of sociocultural competence was directly related to the growing trend of learning any foreign language and the intermingling of different world cultures. The presence of sociocultural competence in a person and the components that are the basis for its formation have been intensively studied in recent decades. In addition to foreign researchers, this article will discuss the work of scientists who studied this competence in coordination with the needs of the education system of Kazakhstan.

Literature review

During the analysis of social and cultural competence on a theoretical and methodological basis, it is necessary to consider the origin of this competence. The American linguist N. Chomsky reintroduced the concept of competence in teaching a foreign language into the circulation of science [5]. In his studying, the concept of competence is described as consisting of a set of abilities aimed at the implementation of linguistic activity.

Over time, the content of the concept of competence increased, and the components or sub-competencies that are part of it began to be studied individually. Among them, its communicative competence within the framework of language competence was mentioned for the first time in the work of the American sociolinguist D. Hymes [6]. According to his description, cognitive and social factors interact in knowing and using a foreign language within the framework of communicative competence.

It has become known that this communicative competence, which has not lost its relevance, but is considered the main prerequisite for learning a foreign language, cannot guarantee the success of intercultural